

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF YOUTH EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article focuses on how to educate young people, build a sense of spiritual sensitivity in the minds of young people and introduce various new correspondent proposals. Theoretical citations are also provided for the practical proof of the idea proposed by the subject.

Key words. Education, learning thirst, noble qualities, faith, spiritual perfection, national anti-doping, inner motivation, social incentive.

From time immemorial, concepts such as thirst for knowledge and enlightenment, tendency to new things, broad imagination and worldview have been ingrained in the blood of our people. The fact that the mature scientists who have contributed to the world civilization, recognized by the whole humanity, have flourished in the borders of our common Motherland, Central Asia, is a clear proof of our opinion. It is a fact of life that in today's fast-moving era, young people are moving away from the path of exemplary ways walked by our great ancestors and are becoming captives of transient, temporarily necessary material technology. The most terrible thing is that various vices, destructive ideas, and painful issues such as a pessimistic view of the future are emerging at the root of these processes. Our great grandfather Mir Alisher Navoi in his epic "Hayrat ul-Abror":

Bow your head to the spoon,

They wrote down a very meaningful thought [1 B-240]. No one has the right to ignore the unpleasant things happening around them. In particular, developing the spirituality of the young generation, providing proper education should be one of our most important tasks.

Our first President, Islam Karimov, wrote in his work "High spirituality - indomitable power" that "It should be noted with pleasure that noble qualities and aspirations are embedded in the blood and bones of our people." The high spirituality characteristic of his nature has been protecting us from various calamities, floods and storms for centuries," [2 B-3.] he said for no reason. In fact, issues of spiritual maturity and consistent education show how important they are today. Thinking is the source of the right life factor in a person. It is through thinking that we analyze existence and express our social reaction to all phenomena. At the heart of the main goal of enriching the thinking of our modern youth is the task of turning these relations into important common

goals. Educating young people to become mentally and physically mature, helping them to take their place in society, and forming their personal abilities are part of the targeted actions.

In the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" developed by President Shavkat Mirziyoev [3 B-10], various reforms, effective projects, and strategic plans that are being carried out in our country have been developed under the "Priority Areas of Social Sector Development" developed. This source entered our socio-political life as a logical continuation of the "Uzbek national model" started by the first President Islam Karimov with great intentions and became our main action program. The theoretical and practical confirmation of the state policy regarding youth, spiritual and educational reforms that we are referring to today is also determined in this important source.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Organize the Activities of the National Anti-Doping Agency under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on January 3 [4 B-1/4] is aimed at the education of healthy young athletes. Implementation of the national anti-doping agency system, development of normative legal documents, working with advanced methods and technologies in the field of anti-doping, expansion of international cooperation, and other similar tasks are all aimed at the growth of our physically healthy and energetic young athletes, and the comprehensive results that our country is achieving in sports. aimed at sustainability. All of this prevents the problems faced by young people, and serves as a program for them to walk on a clearly targeted path.

- It is known that science and technology are rapidly developing. Young people are showing their aspirations on many fronts. Alisher Nazar, a creative publicist, in his article "Need of Soul" said, "There is a secret to the achievements and successes achieved throughout the history of mankind. Faith was the source of the idea of our ancestors. They had correctly found a liberating bond that would pull those attached to it from the quagmire, a law of life superior to any ... isms and pisms devised by the human mind. Human rights, the interests of the Motherland and the nation are protected in every sentence of this statute," [5 B-365] expressed unique opinions. Perhaps, the fact that our young people are taking an example from the lively, light-hearted moral streets of globalization, from the concrete manifestations of the flow of "mass culture" that has spread all over the world, is a sign of the disappearance of the emphasized concept of "faith". If we really look into the past, we will see that the Islamic education of

our forefathers was complete, educated in all aspects, and most importantly, not "mass", but on the contrary, the necessary "moral culture" prevailed.

- If we quote an excerpt from the novel "Gone Days" by the great writer of Uzbek literature, Abdulla Qadiri, "Otabek left the hotel to perform ablution for night prayer, and he said:

- "He is his father's son," Ziya Shahichi looked at the guests.

- "May he live long," said Haji Akram, "he is the smartest among our young men..."

- If it were in my power to raise a khan, I would raise Otabek as a khan.. Did he read it himself?" [6 B-16]. In this small piece alone, you can see the unique description and literary image of Otabek, the artistic ideal of Uzbek youth. The blessed Islamic upbringing, manners, and most importantly, intellectual maturity in it are vividly depicted with extremely important artistic colors through the dialogues of the characters.

- At this point, in order to strengthen the goal of the coverage of this current topic, and ultimately to achieve the promising results of spiritual growth in young people, various corresponding proposals were developed:

-- At a time when the education system is developed in our country, in parallel, based on the interests of the younger generation, attract them to various practical circles. For example, directing the child to an activity he is interested in, such as swimming, drawing. Although the individual does not become a swimmer or an artist, but most importantly, it fills the void in the heart. Forms inner aspiration, growing abilities. In this case, the result is an excellent light on light.

-- Expanding the scope of social incentives. It is necessary to encourage materially and morally the young people who are actively working in any field. The main criterion of human psychology and nature also shows a tendency to love and attention, encouragement and praise.

-- Formation of reading culture among young people. Donation of books as a gift of the President not only for schoolchildren, but also for teenagers, young people in other fields.

-- Reproduction of educational works of art, regular holding of various contests and contests.

-- Spiritual development and strengthening of competition, innovative ideas, working with enterprising youth audiences. By strengthening the role of practice in the OTM system, the skills of young people can be further improved.

The combination of theory and practice in the field of experience gives positive results.

-- Training of qualified psychologists and pedagogues. It is better to apply the principle of working more closely with young people. It must be admitted that there are many good, experienced specialists in their field in our country, but there are few experienced pedagogues. The modern trend of the tradition of "teacher-student" means communication between the pedagogical personnel and the youth.

- Fundamental reform of the internet system in our country. It is necessary to train qualified personnel in the field.

- Exchange of experience with foreign countries with rapid development of science and technology.

- Every household should have Uzbek national musical instruments, and growing children should learn to play them and develop in a purely national spirit.

- Establishment of madrasas. It is necessary to achieve the formation of pure Islamic education in a certain period of time.

Acquiring knowledge and wisdom enriches the spirituality of any person. The formation of young thinking is directly related to the newly formed ideological field, the existence of spiritual regions hungry for knowledge, and the activity of the brain hungry for information. That is why it is said that "Knowledge acquired in youth is like a pattern carved in stone." Propagators of various foreign ideas gather young people into their destructive gangs, realizing these aspects.

To sum up, important reforms such as development of youth education, improvement of moral maturity, increase of active youth in the society should be intensified. As the young seeker Khurshid Yoldoshev slowly leafed through the "mind notebook looking for his Arastus", he realized the superiority of the criterion of learning in its essence and began to write in his articles. [7 B-28] So, we can find solutions to various problems by studying and learning. At the bottom of the policy of developed strong countries, attention to education has been formed. Realizing our spiritual connection to the effect of the many spiritual reforms being implemented in our country, let's unite the youth towards one goal! After all, education begins with self-awareness and striving for tomorrow. We are confident that the Motherland will help us in this way!

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